

RESIDENTS' SATISFACTION OF HOUSING: DISSATISFACTION ASSESSMENT OF PUBLIC HOUSING ESTATE IN ILORIN.

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Abstract

This study examines residents' satisfaction of public housing estates in Ilorin. Several literatures were reviewed and many theories applied. Both primary and secondary data were sourced using questionnaire, participant observation and interview technique. 303 questionnaires were administered using stratified-systematic sampling method. Simple percentage was used to measure satisfaction on each satisfaction variables considered while stepwise multiple regression was adapted for measuring predictors of satisfaction. The findings revealed that Agba-Dam housing estate ranked first in over-all average satisfaction with 56%. Three variables X10 (Water supply), X3 (Quality of building material), X7 (Electricity) emerged as the predictor of satisfaction with joint contribution of 88.4% rendering other variables insignificant. The study recommends that basic infrastructure and amenities particularly water supply should be provided in a sufficient, qualitative and sustainable manner and government is encouraged to continue to provide housing for people such that the Millennium Development Goals could be achieved and the poor taken good care of among others.

INTRODUCTION

Background to the study

For a long time, geographers, architects, town planners as well as engineers talking about housing have concerned themselves with the physical artifacts and

structural designs of housing provision until recently when interest is shifted towards occupier's satisfaction of housing. Residential satisfaction is more than considering just the technical quality of the constituent components of the building; it also includes how well the housing has met the needs and expectations of the occupiers (Olatubara and Fatoye, 2006). Housing rank second to food in terms of human need and has profound impact on health, well being and productivity of individual (Grimes, 1976). The perception of housing usually give less preference to important components of housing such as space, utilities, community facilities and services, energy and water supply, sewage, as well as accessible roads.

Colonial quarters for expatriate were equivalent of public housing estate before the government formerly got involved in housing provision. Nigeria in its National Development Plan(1975-1980) heralded the provision of public residential estate to meet the increasing housing needs. Public housing estate which is supposed to have basic infrastructural facilities and services such as good roads water supply, electricity e.t.c to enhance the livability of housing estate are usually found lacking in these services. This condition undoubtedly has influence on the level of satisfaction of residents . Housing facilities should be a target of residents through evaluation of occupant's satisfaction that should form realistic basis for housing standard and quality (Mukhtar 2005). The propensity of the household to derive any meaningful satisfaction from unit of housing is predicated on a wide variety of factors like water supply and road network. However, a good understanding of what constitute satisfaction of occupier's of housing will assist in re-focusing priorities of various stakeholders in building public estate. Government is increasing the number of public estate in Ilorin. This is expected to have a corresponding improvement on facilities provided.

The evaluative criterion is as important as public housing provision itself. This study examines the residents' satisfaction of public housing estate in Ilorin with the specific objective of assessing the level of residents' dissatisfaction; examining the differences in characteristics of the estates; and determining variables of

dissatisfaction of residents.

Study Area

Ilorin, the study area, became the capital of Kwara State after the state creation of 27 May, 1967. Kwara State is bounded by Niger State in the North, Kogi State in the East, Oyo, Ekiti and Osun State in the South and the international boundary with republic of Benin in the West. Ilorin is located on Latitude 8'30N and longitude 4'35E (Kwara State Diary, 1997; Figure 1)

Ilorin exhibits dual physical segments: the traditional and modern. The traditional areas are predominantly inhabited by the indigenes while the modern areas are occupied by mainly immigrants and few indigenes. Ilorin has seven public housing estates out of which five are state owned. The state- owned are Agba Dam, Adewole, Mandate 1, Mandate 11 and Irewolede housing estates (Kwara State Properties Development Cooperation, 2007). Oloje Low Cost Housing Estates and Kulende estate are the Federal Government -owned public housing estates in Ilorin. The population of Ilorin stood at 532,519 (NPC 1991) with an expected annual growth rate of 2.85% in 1996. Today, Ilorin metropolis has a population of 777,667 (NPC 2006).

Conceptual Clarifications and Literature Review

Housing at its basic level is certainly shelter, but it is equally much more than that. Housing rank second generally among the basic necessities of man.

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Figure 1.1: Map of Kwara State Showing the Study Area
 Source: Kwara State Land and Housing, 2003

Atolagbe (2007) describes housing as an advance or more sophisticated stage of shelter plus a sanitary and a conducive living environment; the latter include educational, market, transportation, recreational, shopping, security facilities, privacy and so on. Provision of housing is necessitated by a high demand for it, particularly in the urban area as a result of uncontrolled urbanization. However, provision of housing cannot be said to be successful until it meets the needs and expectation of occupiers which is to a large extent determined by numerous variables.

Housing as a concept is as old as history of man's consciousness for a defined settlement rather than wandering. Housing has been viewed as a physical entity ranked among the basic need of man. It usually has tremendous impact on one's life style, state of mind, health as well as productivity. Atolagbe (2007) views housing as a modern contraption of the historic "shelter" which has physical space enclosed for protection of man from element of weather. Adedibu (1980) is of the opinion that "the concept of shelter as a simple dwelling does not only preventt people from some element like rain, excessive heat and cold but a place to dwell with comfort". Awani (1980) gives the concept of housing by drawing a line between housing as a process and housing a product. He opines that the former entail all steps and procedures in the activities leading to the acquisition of a house, while the later concerns the resulting unit together with its enabling environment.

Efobi (1992) conceives housing as more than provision of houses. It involves the act of providing shelter, lodging and covers the process of producing houses ranging from acquisition of land for housing development to the sub - division of the layout in which cognizance is taken of the ancillary. Consequently, United Nation Centre for Human Settlement (UNCHS 1996) agrees that housing is broadly more than having a roof over one's head. It implies protection from disposal of household and human wastes as well as sufficient space. A good house should therefore be able to provide for privacy, security, tenure of occupancy, safe drinking water, affordability and access to employment, health, recreation and educational services.

Housing as a concept thus transcends the physically sound structure for shelter at affordable prices but also a suitable size and location which meet the need of the household. The neighborhood environment should be able to function in a manner that will provide adequate supply of housing related services. In other words, housing should be used to cover all accepted ways by which man acquires a territory of his own with availability of all social infrastructure services and all necessities of life.

Occupier's satisfaction could be seen as the fulfillment he obtains when the house meets his needs (such as water supply and good roads). Fatoye and Olatubara (2006) in their study on residential satisfaction of public estate in Lagos assert that occupiers are most satisfied with criteria under Functional element which include; layout of rooms, location of rooms and availability of parking space. Their findings further revealed that occupiers are least satisfied with behavior element which includes security of the estate and nearness of the house to workspace. Ayinla et al (2004) used environment and physical variables of housing to measure satisfaction of residential students. The finding reveals that students are dissatisfied majorly with environmental variables which include poor security and unclean environment.

In a similar vein, Odunjo et al (2006) assessed the condition of buildings and infrastructural facilities in a core traditional neighborhood of Ibadan with a motive of determining their potentialities for meeting the housing needs of the residents. The study showed that over 60 percent of the houses fall short of resident (occupiers) need and satisfaction. He recommended that government policy should be reviewed to involve the participation of public and private agencies as well as Non Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Toscano and Victoria (2007) examined the determinant of individual and household satisfaction and social service in Spain using physical service variables. The study showed that individuals are most satisfied with household attributes such as room size, number of rooms and kitchen size than social service like recreation.

Methodology

This study made use of data from both primary and secondary source. The primary data was obtained through the use of structured questionnaire, interview and participant observation. In addition to ones obtained from the library, the secondary data were generated from government agencies such as Kwara State Property and Development Agency (KSPDA), Ilorin; Ministry of Lands and Housing; and Federal Ministry of Housing and Urban Development, Ilorin. Questionnaires were administered to 15% of heads of household using systematic selection of every 5 house in all the estates making a total of 303 questionnaires.

The methods employed in the analysis of data for this study were both the descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive methods include the use of frequency distribution, simple percentages and tables. While the inferential statistics involved the stepwise multiple regression analysis to measure satisfaction index of residents. Olawepo (2003) used this method to measure the spatioeconomic impact of community banks in participatory development in Kwara State. This is thus summarized as $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_nX_n + e$

Where Y = Residents' dissatisfaction as the independent variable. The dependent variables are

X_1 = size of bathrooms/toilet

X_2 = size of room

X_3 = quality of materials used in the building

X_4 = number of bathrooms/toilets

X_5 = size of kitchen

X_6 = number of rooms

X_7 = Electricity

X_8 = Aesthetics

X_9 = security

X_{10} = water supply

X_{11} = open space

X_{12} = recreational

X_{13} = road network

X_{14} = drainage

a = intercept

$b_x b_{xi}$ = regression coefficient

e = error term

Results and Discussion

Ownership distribution of respondents

Ownership status of houses of the estates revealed that 62% of the respondents are occupiers by rent while 38% of respondents are owner occupiers (Table 1). The implication of this is that majority of the estate residents are tenants which is a departure from the owner occupiers' policy.

Table I Ownership Status of Respondents

Status	Number of Respondents	Percentage of Respondents
Ownership Occupiers	116	38
Rental Occupiers	187	62
Total	303	100

Sources: Fieldwork, 2008

Dissatisfaction of residents

The over-all average percentage dissatisfaction as contained in Table 3, revealed that Agba-dam estate ranked top with the highest occupier's dissatisfaction of 56%. This could be as a result of its size with just four buildings couple with the fact that it was constructed long time ago. Also, its location is not that accessible from many part of the town. Kulende Estate followed in second place with 55% over-all dissatisfaction . Mandate 1 and Oloje estate jointly trail in the third position with 42%

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dissatisfaction. This could be as a result of Oloje's location which is not far from city-core area. Also, it is the first low cost housing estate with large number of housing unit. occupied fourth position with dissatisfaction of 41%, Irewolede fifth position with 40%. Mandate II has the least dissatisfaction of 38%. This could be as a result of it being the newest among the housing estate with clean environment. The spatial variation of occupiers' over-all percentage dissatisfaction of public housing estate in Ilorin could be attributed to the differentiation in their year of construction, owning government, size and location.

OCCUPIERS' DISSATISFACTION DETERMINING FACTORS

In order to explain the probable factor or factors contributing to residents' dissatisfaction of public residential estate in Ilorin, fourteen variables were considered. A stepwise multiple regression analysis was carried out with residents' satisfaction of public housing estate as the dependent variable and factors X_1 to X_{14} as the independent variables. Of all the 14 variables, three were found to be significant at the specified tolerance level of 0.50 for entry into the model. These are X_{10} (Water supply), X_3 (Quality of material), and X_7 (Electricity) (See table 4).

Table 4. STEPWISE MULTIPLE REGRESSION OF OCCUPIERS' DISSATISFACTION DETERMINING FACTORS

Variables	Parameter estimate	Standard error	R	R ²	% percentage of contribution	t- test	Cumulative Percentage contribution
Intercepts	3.912	1.104					
X_{10}	1.728	0.093	0.786	0.790	79.0	19.791	79.0
X_3	1.015	0.093	0.844	0.844	8.5	2.914	8.5
X_7	0.876	0.059	0.853	0.801	0.9	1.549	0.9
							88.4

Source: Author's computer output 2008.

According to the out outcome of the stepwise multiple regression analysis (Table 4) water (X_{10}) of the estate is probably the best predictor of occupiers' dissatisfaction. The correlation coefficient of this variable is 0.786 and r^2 of 0.790 with a percentage contribution of 79% variance. This could be attributed to inefficient water system within the estates, which leaves individual at the mercy of self provision of water supply. This comes in form of well, boreholes and water tanker. Quality of building materials x_3 was the next determinant. It has a correlation coefficient of 0.844 with a percentage contribution of 8.5%. This is evident on the building as many occupiers claim to have changed many things they perceived to be substandard or inferior in the houses. Other contributing factor to dissatisfaction is electricity (X_7) with percentage contribution of 0.9%. The reason for this could be attributed to the fact that energy or electricity is a problem in the state and Nigeria as a whole, which makes this case not to be in isolation of general societal problem. The three variables collectively account for 85.3% variance of dissatisfaction. The remaining eleven variables are not significant in explaining their contributions to satisfaction because the coefficient value are too low to offer any meaningful explanation of their varied pattern. The regression for occupiers' dissatisfaction could thus be written as ; $Y = 0.657 + 1.728(X_{10}) + 1.015 X_3 + 0.876 X_7$. Where Y =Dissatisfaction of residents.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Resident's dissatisfaction revealed that Agba-Dam estates ranked first with over-all dissatisfaction of 56% followed by Kulende estate with 55% dissatisfaction. Three out of the fourteen dissatisfaction variables dissatisfaction. There out of the fourteen dissatisfaction variables considered emerged as predictor of dissatisfaction. Water supply X_{10} has the highest contribution to dissatisfaction with 79%. Other variable of dissatisfaction include electricity x_7 , with percentage contribution of 0.9% and Quality of material x_3 , with dissatisfaction contribution of 8.5% recreation and drainage. Availability of open space X_{11} accounted for highest percentage

contribution of 52% of satisfaction. Other variable of dissatisfaction are recreation and drainage.

General dissatisfaction of housing may be difficult to achieve because it varies as a result of individual differences, however it is the dream of everyone to be able to stay in houses where convenience and comfort are guaranteed. Individuals and government in particular have often tried to achieve this with continuous effort at providing public housing. Housing problem should be considered an urban menace which needs to be taken serious so as to be able to reduce dissatisfaction.

Based on the outcome of the study the following are recommended with a view to improving quality of public estate provision for sustainable occupiers' satisfaction.

- i. Provision of basic infrastructural and amenities particularly, portable water supply in a sufficient, quality and sustainable level.
- ii. Government should make 'Performance Evaluation' of already existing housing estates a priority so as to identify areas that need to be improved upon in the subsequent housing estate construction.
- iii. Government through the housing agency should include the occupier by ownership clause in the acquisition of the house in order to discourage and reduce the rentage of house in the estate at exorbitant fee which negates the principle that brought about public housing provision.
- iv. Occupiers should be discouraged from distorting the structures through expansion of land and housing reconstruction as this will limit the number of open space which are contributing to good health.
- v. Government should be able to divorce politics from social service provision by giving the public housing construction responsibilities to housing professionals who would cater and care for physical, environmental and social needs of the eventual occupier right from the design of the construction stage. Housing satisfaction remains relative, even in the most advanced country of the world where everything is in order and well-planned with

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modern infrastructure and amenities, occupiers still get dissatisfied with one thing or the other. Nevertheless, satisfaction of resident's public housing will be tremendously enhanced and improved if these recommendations are taken into consideration. Government is encouraged to continue to provide housing for the people such that the Millennium Development Goals would be achieved and the poor would be taken good care of.

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